

Rapid Electroanalytical Method of Estimation of Rhenium

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Rhenium can be estimated by the quantitative electrodeposition on a platinum-gauge cathode from a solution of perrhenate in 5% sulphuric acid¹. The method was improved and applied in micro-determination by Tomíček and Tomíček². In the original method of Lundell and Knowles¹, the electrolysis is carried out overnight at room temperature with stationary electrodes and as such the time required for complete deposition is too long. They have also shown that the electrolyte still contains certain amount of rhenium, but the results are high due to oxidation of the deposit. The results obtained by the later workers with stationary electrodes on a micro-scale were still higher owing probably to the smaller amounts of metal deposited and to the higher temperature used. For a more accurate determination, they oxidised the deposit to perrhenic acid and estimated it acidimetrically. The time required in their method is still more than three hours. We have, however, observed that the analysis can be performed within a much shorter period with reasonable accuracy by a little modification of their methods.

Procedure.—The electrolyte was a solution of potassium perrhenate in 2*N*-H₂SO₄, kept at 70-75°. This was electrolysed with a rotatory platinum anode and a fixed platinum-gauge cathode for 60 to 75 minutes. After the electrolysis the gauge was first washed with water without disconnecting the mains. The washing was finally completed with acetone; it was quickly dried in air and then at 105° for 30 seconds. The gauge was then cooled in a desiccator over H₂SO₄ (conc.) for 15 minutes and weighed. The electrolyte after electrolysis was found to contain only traces of rhenium. Some of the analyses are shown below. The results are high within 1%.

Re taken (mg.)	..	10.5	20.2	21.1	30.3
Re found (mg.)	..	10.5	20.4	21.3	30.4

Thanks of the authors are due to Prof. P. B. Sarkar, Dr. es. Sc., F.N.I., for his keen interest and suggestion.

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Received June 25, 1963.

1. Lundell and Knowles, *Res. Natl. Bur. Standards*, 1937, 18, 629.
2. *Trans. Electrochem. Soc.*, 1939, 76, 105.

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